

BIOPLASTICS BASED ON POTATO AND COFFEE BY-PRODUCTS FOR ACTIVE CARDBOARD COATING

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Abstract: *Cardboard is widely used in packaging due to its biodegradability, lightness, and recyclability. However, its hydrophilic nature and porous fibre network limit water vapor barrier properties and compromise mechanical strength, particularly under humid conditions. To overcome these limitations, cardboard is often coated with synthetic polymers or aluminium. However, these coatings decrease biodegradability and recyclability, undermining the environmental benefits of fibre-based packaging. Sustainable alternatives based on agri-food by-products have gained attention as environmentally compatible coatings. As part of the BIOCOATING project, this work focuses on the development of biodegradable active coatings for cardboard, using thermoplastic starch obtained from potato washing slurries and enriched with coffee industry by-products, intended for use in paper-based packaging systems. Coffee silverskin (CS) and spent coffee grounds (SCG) were selected for their content in bioactive compounds, including lignin, cellulose, caffeine, and phenolics, which positively influence the performance of the coatings by enhancing antioxidant activity, reducing water vapor permeability, and contributing to mechanical reinforcement. The starch extracted from potato washing residues acts as a biodegradable matrix with good film-forming properties. The coatings were produced by thermomechanical blending and applied onto cardboard substrates through hot-pressing. The resulting coated cardboard is expected to exhibit natural pigmentation, enhanced water resistance, and antioxidant activity. By valorising low-value residues from the agri-food sector, this work supports the development of eco-friendly and functionally enhanced cardboard-based packaging materials aligned with circular economy principles.*

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